

Statistical study of the peak and fluence spectra of solar energetic particles observed over four solar cycles

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ABSTRACT

Context. Solar energetic particles (SEPs) are an important space radiation source, especially for the space weather environment in the inner heliosphere. The energy spectrum of SEP events is crucial both for evaluating their radiation effects and for understanding their acceleration process at the source region, along with their propagation mechanism.

Aims. In this work, we investigate the properties of the SEP peak flux spectra and the fluence spectra and their potential formation mechanisms using statistical methods. We aim to advance our understanding of SEP acceleration and propagation mechanisms.

Methods. Employing a dataset from the European Space Agency's Solar Energetic Particle Environment Modelling (SEP-EM) program, we obtained and fit the peak-flux and fluence proton spectra of more than a hundred SEP events from 1974 to 2018. We analyzed the relationship among the solar activity, X-ray peak intensity of solar flares, and the SEP's spectral parameters.

Results. Based on the assumption that the initial spectrum of accelerated SEPs generally displays a power-law distribution and that the diffusion coefficient has a power-law dependence on the particle energy, we can assess both the source and propagation properties using the observed SEP event peak flux and fluence energy spectra. We confirm that the spectral properties of SEPs are influenced by the solar source and the interplanetary conditions, whereas their transportation process can be influenced by different phases of solar cycle.

Conclusions. This study provides an observational perspective on the double power-law spectral characteristics of the SEP energy spectra, revealing their correlation with the adiabatic cooling and diffusion processes during the particle propagation from the Sun to the observer. This result contributes to forging a deeper understanding of the acceleration and propagation of SEP events, in particular, the possible origins of the double power law.

Key words. Sun: particle emission–Sun: activity–Sun: flares–sunspots–Diffusion

Table 3. Peak flux spectral parameters fitted for 103 events.

No.No.	Start Time	End Time	j_0^2	j_0	j_0	α	α_{err}	κ_0	κ_0	κ_0	κ_0	γ	γ_{err}	V_{sw}^5	V_{sw}	χ^2
1	1974-07-03 01:00	1974-07-10 13:30	4.02E+07	2.91E+07	1.49	0.33	2.41E+19	2.41E+19	1.72E+19	5	0.15	571.96	122.74	24.6		
2	1977-09-18 16:30	1977-09-23 07:30	1.32E+06	1.27E+06	0.93	0.2	5.26E+19	5.26E+19	2.22E+19	3.43	0.16	407.1	40.59	3.81		
3	1977-11-22 11:00	1977-11-28 13:30	2.72E+06	2.46E+06	1.21	0.15	2.87E+19	8.24E+18	3.28E+18	3.31	0.16	351.04	65.76	6.15		
4	1978-02-13 08:00	1978-02-22 21:30	3.40E+06	5.38E+05	2.81	0.87	3.24E+10	3.10E+18	5.80E+18	4.03	0.04	412.58	77.81	20.6		
5	1978-04-08 04:00	1978-04-16 03:00	1.10E+08	3.49E+08	0.72	0.14	3.45E+19	3.45E+19	9.17E+18	4.3	0.45	491.45	76.29	16.31		
6	1978-04-17 03:30	1978-05-05 02:30	3.69E+06	5.96E+05	3.36	0.87	6.84E+17	6.84E+17	1.27E+18	4.05	0.04	514.36	109.31	33.4		
7	1978-09-23 11:30	1978-10-16 01:30	6.73E+05	7.60E+04	3.58	1.2	4.96E+17	4.96E+17	1.27E+18	3.2	0.03	544.32	150.63	3.46		
8	1979-02-17 16:30	1979-02-23 08:00	1.07E+06	1.33E+06	0.95	0.14	1.08E+19	2.43E+19	7.47E+18	3.7	0.2	509.62	66.95	11.23		
9	1979-09-08 12:00	1979-10-03 04:30	1.99E+05	8.68E+04	1.34	0.23	2.26E+19	2.26E+19	1.17E+19	3.52	0.08	322.92	16.64	6.87		
10	1980-02-05 18:30	1980-02-09 18:30	5.83E+03	1.10E+03	2.23	0.51	5.36E+18	5.36E+18	6.11E+18	3.13	0.04	426.83	51.93	6.41		
11	1980-03-29 19:30	1980-04-08 20:00	1.35E+04	1.21E+04	1.04	0.19	2.03E+18	2.75E+19	1.22E+19	3.08	0.15	400.85	66.06	5.77		
12	1981-04-24 04:00	1981-04-26 11:00	1.75E+05	7.31E+04	1.48	0.24	1.20E+19	1.20E+19	7.04E+18	3.18	0.08	477.98	66.89	18.84		
13	1981-07-20 15:00	1981-07-28 07:00	7.40E+05	1.07E+06	0.78	0.2	8.76E+18	7.58E+19	3.42E+19	3.62	0.22	494.18	124.13	11.15		
14	1981-10-08 03:30	1981-10-26 22:30	1.14E+06	8.33E+05	0.91	0.61	2.51E+20	2.51E+20	3.10E+20	3.38	0.12	439.16	71.41	5.88		
15	1981-12-05 17:00	1981-12-14 08:00	2.23E+05	3.54E+04	6.91	10.46	4.85E+19	2.66E+15	5.39E+16	4.18	0.05	353.87	64.71	0.11		
16	1984-03-07 01:00	1984-03-23 07:00	1.67E+04	9.78E+03	0.79	0.17	2.10E+19	9.27E+19	3.64E+19	2.73	0.08	525.95	44.12	1.93		
17	1984-04-25 09:30	1984-05-15 19:30	3.78E+06	5.00E+05	2.97	0.51	5.13E+19	9.53E+17	1.08E+18	3.86	0.03	534	11.86	43.56		
18	1985-07-12 13:30	1985-07-12 13:30	5.33E+04	1.25E+04	1.9	0.27	8.03E+19	4.90E+18	3.32E+18	3.21	0.05	471.66	57.1	9.26		
19	1986-02-19 10:55	1986-02-19 07:40	1.06E+05	1.27E+04	3.26	0.63	1.38E+19	4.88E+17	6.90E+17	3.37	0.03	479.32	45.99	5.88		
20	1986-05-04 12:20	1986-05-05 13:15	2.47E+05	7.16E+05	0.75	0.22	2.27E+19	5.45E+19	1.85E+19	3.75	0.45	416.78	21.79	1.35		
21	1987-11-07 22:45	1987-11-10 13:15	4.65E+07	7.61E+07	1.3	0.25	1.75E+19	1.59E+19	8.25E+18	5.24	0.33	530.58	107.19	0.17		
22	1988-11-08 15:45	1988-11-10 11:40	1.47E+02	1.28E+01	4.28	2.82	1.86E+17	1.86E+17	1.09E+18	2.25	0.02	416.87	55	7.21		
23	1989-03-08 03:30	1989-03-14 19:50	3.32E+10	2.32E+10	1.57	0.19	1.08E+19	1.08E+19	5.34E+18	6.42	0.15	543.96	152.17	78.63		
24	1989-03-23 20:15	1989-03-24 21:30	1.37E+04	5.54E+03	1.2	0.78	1.62E+20	1.62E+20	2.71E+20	3.23	0.07	533.33	83.85	20.8		
25	1989-04-10 21:15	1989-04-18 01:45	2.50E+09	6.33E+09	1.08	0.23	2.72E+19	2.72E+19	1.07E+19	6.1	0.48	402.14	30.24	1.66		
26	1989-07-25 09:05	1989-07-26 17:45	5.90E+02	1.26E+02	1.37	0.24	1.66E+19	1.66E+19	9.97E+18	2.07	0.04	432.62	36.96	5.74		
27	1989-08-12 15:45	1989-08-14 15:45	3.02E+07	4.87E+06	2.1	0.16	1.48E+18	1.48E+18	6.96E+17	3.87	0.03	530.51	92.08	42.99		
28	1989-09-29 11:55	1989-10-10 05:20	1.30E+05	2.30E+04	1.55	0.26	1.32E+19	1.32E+19	8.74E+18	2.39	0.03	394.27	25.07	8.29		
29	1989-10-19 13:10	1989-11-09 16:50	1.15E+07	1.12E+06	2.68	0.6	1.55E+20	2.49E+18	3.44E+18	3.15	0.02	609.32	150.42	12.75		
30	1989-11-27 06:25	1989-12-05 09:05	5.52E+08	1.37E+08	2.7	0.24	4.64E+17	4.64E+17	2.74E+17	5.2	0.05	554.5	85.57	90.49		
31	1990-03-19 06:30	1990-03-22 01:40	1.31E+10	8.51E+09	1.78	0.14	2.67E+18	2.67E+18	1.08E+18	6.28	0.13	447.1	96.56	60.07		
32	1990-05-17 21:30	1990-05-24 19:00	2.09E+04	2.36E+03	1.93	2.05	7.12E+19	7.13E+19	3.26E+20	2.57	0.02	418.11	62.97	4.31		
33	1990-07-31 15:25	1990-08-06 12:05	2.52E+12	1.84E+13	0.83	0.2	2.47E+19	3.03E+19	7.69E+18	7.28	1.21	441	60.6	0.88		
34	1991-01-27 14:45	1991-02-02 19:30	1.14E+07	2.79E+06	3.45	0.48	8.68E+18	2.19E+17	2.32E+17	5.02	0.06	376.37	33.78	3.28		
35	1991-02-25 10:40	1991-02-27 01:55	8.17E+03	1.57E+03	3.92	0.89	5.58E+18	1.08E+17	2.07E+17	3.46	0.05	422.79	48.27	47.11		
36	1991-03-12 18:50	1991-03-13 22:25	2.50E+05	5.50E+05	1.15	0.32	2.34E+19	2.34E+19	1.37E+19	4.19	0.43	363.9	27.61	0.34		
37	1991-03-23 06:40	1991-03-31 14:30	2.87E+08	4.12E+07	2.49	0.21	1.13E+19	8.15E+17	4.39E+17	4.12	0.03	478.67	13.01	61.51		
38	1991-05-10 15:05	1991-05-15 10:50	5.20E+04	4.11E+03	3.9	1.24	7.11E+19	2.47E+17	6.51E+17	2.97	0.02	364.81	13.16	10.25		
39	1991-06-09 19:10	1991-06-15 01:30	3.57E+06	6.14E+05	2.01	0.19	1.91E+18	1.91E+18	1.02E+18	3.42	0.03	541.21	73.29	18.18		
40	1991-08-25 21:10	1991-08-30 22:30	1.66E+08	2.48E+08	1.26	0.27	5.86E+19	2.48E+19	1.36E+19	5.51	0.31	435.36	79.36	2.27		
41	1992-02-06 22:45	1992-02-10 00:30	1.71E+07	1.20E+07	2.63	0.73	2.32E+19	2.45E+18	3.60E+18	5.57	0.19	461.75	58.05	0.61		
42	1992-05-09 06:15	1992-05-13 20:15	6.84E+09	2.09E+09	2.29	0.21	1.91E+18	1.91E+18	1.13E+18	6.04	0.07	429.13	150.13	54.45		
43	1992-06-25 20:30	1992-07-01 23:25	1.91E+04	1.58E+03	3.79	0.79	7.56E+18	1.10E+17	1.98E+17	2.61	0.02	536.66	41.41	10.18		
44	1992-10-30 18:45	1992-11-01 21:20	5.29E+06	7.49E+05	4.19	0.49	6.46E+15	6.46E+15	8.09E+15	3.75	0.03	404.82	28.12	50.09		

Table 3. continued.

No.No./	Start Time	End Time	j_0^2	$j_0 \cdot \text{err}^2$	α	$\alpha \cdot \text{err}$	$\kappa_0 \cdot 450^3$	κ_0^4	$\kappa_0 \cdot \text{err}^4$	γ	$\gamma \cdot \text{err}$	V_{sw}^3	$V_{sw} \cdot \text{err}^3 \cdot \chi^2$
45	134	1993-03-04 13:20	1.20E+03	2.31E+02	1.87	0.89	2.55E+19	2.55E+19	5.05E+19	2.64	0.04	416.61	77.49
46	136	1993-03-12 18:50	2.98E+03	5.88E+02	1.69	0.89	4.50E+19	4.50E+19	8.95E+19	2.63	0.04	520.48	40.97
47	140	1997-11-04 06:50	9.73E+08	9.04E+09	0.33	0.12	1.01E+20	1.19E+20	1.94E+19	3.59	0.82	371.21	38.3
48	141	1998-04-26 15:05	4.52E+08	1.68E+08	2.76	0.19	1.19E+18	4.88E+16	2.76E+16	4.79	0.08	406.23	24.61
49	143	1998-05-02 13:55	9.54E+03	1.70E+03	1.51	0.23	1.34E+19	1.34E+19	8.12E+18	2.47	0.03	547.41	3.7
50	144	1998-05-06 08:25	8.13E+04	1.10E+04	3.7	0.47	1.54E+16	1.54E+16	1.95E+16	3.07	0.03	497.11	48.28
51	145	1998-05-09 06:50	1.73E+05	2.25E+06	0.52	0.69	1.62E+20	1.62E+20	6.19E+19	3.7	1.77	426.97	2.12
52	149	1998-09-30 14:25	7.04E+06	1.83E+06	2.21	0.23	1.57E+18	1.57E+18	9.53E+17	4.06	0.05	474.22	88.81
53	152	1998-11-14 06:30	5.28E+05	2.14E+05	1.52	0.17	1.76E+19	6.62E+18	2.93E+18	3.41	0.08	432.73	51.39
54	156	1999-05-27 12:15	8.15E+04	2.70E+05	1.02	0.36	3.29E+19	2.62E+19	1.51E+19	3.72	0.61	388.59	35.9
55	158	2000-02-18 08:45	2.33E+03	8.73E+02	1.45	0.43	2.94E+19	2.94E+19	2.95E+19	2.88	0.07	436.73	136.37
56	161	2000-06-10 04:00	3.68E+04	3.66E+04	0.86	0.22	6.65E+19	6.65E+19	3.15E+19	3.09	0.16	540.76	84.83
57	163	2000-07-13 00:30	1.57E+07	2.03E+06	2.33	0.2	6.29E+17	6.29E+17	3.81E+17	3.22	0.02	661.16	135.08
58	166	2000-09-12 14:50	1.07E+06	1.38E+05	5.13	1.45	1.02E+18	1.82E+16	5.45E+16	4.19	0.03	478.27	154
59	168	2000-10-25 15:15	7.27E+03	9.58E+02	6.72	58.72	2.19E+16	2.19E+16	2.48E+18	3.42	0.04	377.28	32.77
60	170	2000-11-15 17:00	2.84E+11	1.43E+11	1.27	0.05	4.05E+18	3.14E+18	9.34E+17	5.21	0.08	605.41	151.47
61	171	2000-11-24 07:00	1.63E+04	1.88E+03	3.18	1.2	1.34E+18	1.34E+18	3.44E+18	3.01	0.03	497.56	71.98
62	176	2001-04-02 11:20	1.42E+07	3.18E+06	3.38	0.3	1.57E+16	1.57E+16	1.38E+16	4.1	0.05	548.41	96.53
63	178	2001-05-07 15:00	2.73E+04	4.38E+03	5.25	2.29	1.96E+16	1.96E+16	9.11E+16	3.67	0.04	474.33	80.86
64	179	2001-05-20 08:45	1.46E+02	2.16E+01	2.84	0.61	5.14E+17	5.14E+17	7.61E+17	2.13	0.03	417.18	87.24
65	182	2001-08-16 00:55	1.21E+07	2.45E+06	2.4	0.14	3.28E+17	7.03E+16	3.44E+16	3.75	0.04	459.33	77.22
66	183	2001-09-24 12:00	1.13E+08	1.96E+07	2.23	0.2	1.61E+18	1.61E+18	8.27E+17	4.2	0.03	508.35	76.6
67	185	2001-11-05 16:55	1.11E+10	3.20E+09	1.43	0.07	4.01E+18	4.01E+18	1.16E+18	4.69	0.05	482.65	98.21
68	186	2001-11-17 19:55	1.01E+11	6.11E+10	1.69	0.13	3.46E+18	3.46E+18	1.52E+18	5.97	0.12	460.88	141.35
69	188	2001-12-26 05:55	2.29E+06	9.54E+05	1.15	0.09	4.08E+18	1.04E+19	3.11E+18	3.23	0.07	416.91	65.95
70	189	2002-01-10 09:55	4.76E+05	1.44E+05	2.7	0.56	8.15E+18	1.72E+18	2.10E+18	4.25	0.08	486.11	86.35
71	191	2002-04-17 11:30	5.53E+07	1.48E+07	1.75	0.12	8.16E+18	2.53E+18	8.57E+17	4.12	0.05	492.63	56.64
72	192	2002-05-22 07:50	3.10E+07	5.56E+06	3.98	1.5	2.15E+18	3.86E+17	1.18E+18	5.1	0.05	555.97	135.26
73	193	2002-07-07 14:00	1.26E+05	1.41E+05	1.61	0.31	5.35E+18	6.03E+18	3.99E+18	3.86	0.24	431.76	44.02
74	200	2002-11-09 17:10	3.29E+07	1.84E+07	2.06	0.29	1.17E+19	3.27E+18	2.13E+18	5.05	0.13	487.19	81.09
75	205	2003-10-28 03:30	2.04E+08	3.53E+07	1.92	0.16	2.99E+18	2.99E+18	1.55E+18	3.96	0.03	663.49	204.97
76	207	2003-12-02 12:50	1.46E+08	1.18E+08	1.7	0.24	7.66E+18	7.66E+18	4.24E+18	5.79	0.18	446.6	89.46
77	209	2004-07-23 15:05	1.68E+10	8.63E+09	2.32	0.22	1.36E+18	1.36E+18	7.55E+17	6.48	0.12	623.09	141.75
78	211	2004-09-13 19:55	2.28E+07	9.11E+06	2.36	0.47	3.97E+18	3.97E+18	4.03E+18	5.08	0.1	484.2	71.98
79	213	2004-11-01 06:10	7.68E+04	2.56E+04	1.94	0.22	1.91E+18	1.91E+18	1.16E+18	3.3	0.07	399.63	86.18
80	214	2004-11-07 02:50	5.25E+06	7.98E+05	3.24	0.46	4.03E+17	4.03E+17	4.25E+17	4.37	0.03	597.56	106.37
81	216	2005-01-20 01:00	2.40E+04	1.57E+04	0.77	0.24	8.12E+19	8.12E+19	4.73E+19	1.74	0.09	694.59	152.67
82	218	2005-05-13 21:00	8.58E+10	3.64E+10	3.04	0.3	3.69E+17	3.69E+17	2.66E+17	7.16	0.11	559.26	137.71
83	219	2005-06-16 20:50	7.78E+03	2.65E+03	1.61	0.23	5.53E+18	5.53E+18	3.35E+18	2.68	0.06	430.04	92.27
84	220	2005-07-13 18:10	1.65E+12	1.18E+13	1.02	0.19	1.05E+19	1.05E+19	2.82E+18	7.01	1.25	443.63	53.29
85	221	2005-07-26 23:20	3.09E+06	3.65E+07	0.49	0.83	3.17E+20	3.17E+20	1.61E+20	4.39	1.58	489.66	78.23
86	224	2006-12-05 17:35	2.08E+06	3.13E+05	2.13	0.31	4.33E+18	4.33E+18	3.23E+18	3.45	0.03	585.02	90.67
87	227	2011-03-07 23:15	1.00E+09	6.67E+09	0.81	0.27	3.94E+19	3.94E+19	1.56E+19	5.64	1.11	438.2	100.95
88	229	2011-06-05 20:05	4.62E+04	4.18E+04	0.89	0.21	5.40E+19	5.40E+19	2.38E+19	2.96	0.14	438	39.49

Table 4. Integral fluence spectral parameters fitted for 164 events.

No.	No. / Start Time	End Time	C ²	γ_1	γ_2	E_0^3	E_{break}^4	C_err ²	γ_1_{err}	γ_2_{err}	$E_0_{err}^3$	$E_{break_{err}}^4$	GLE	Flare	χ^2
1	2	1974-07-03 01:00	1974-07-10 13:30	4.62E+09	-2.3	-5.57	9.44	30.85	1.33E+09	0.18	1.05	7.51			31.24
2	3	1974-09-11 00:00	1974-10-03 18:00	1.98E+09	-2.04	-3.5	8.94	13.1	1.93E+09	0.83	7.18	33.43			23.20
3	4	1974-11-05 07:00	1974-11-08 19:00	2.13E+07	-2.21	-2.98	52.04	39.76	4.44E+06	0.12	16.83	66.78			1.03
4	5	1975-08-21 17:00	1975-08-24 05:00	3.34E+06	-2.06	-3.61	57.53	89.03	4.42E+05	0.06	6.53	31.15			5.09
5	6	1976-04-30 22:00	1976-05-05 03:30	5.78E+07	-1.95	-2.95	116.25	116.12	6.61E+06	0.05	16.8	67.22	Yes	X2	2.29
6	7	1976-08-22 16:30	1976-08-24 23:00	4.50E+06	-1.89	-3.89	19.36	38.79	1.03E+06	0.13	2.71	13.71		M3	18.03
7	9	1977-09-18 16:30	1977-09-23 07:30	4.78E+08	-1.93	-3.32	32.79	45.45	9.03E+07	0.1	5.4	23.08	Yes	X2	1.62
8	11	1977-11-22 11:00	1977-11-28 13:30	6.13E+07	-1.23	-3.12	27.8	52.3	1.05E+07	0.09	3	11.64	Yes	X1	1.83
9	12	1978-01-02 07:30	1978-01-06 16:00	7.58E+06	-1.89	-3.74	22.16	40.95	1.90E+06	0.14	3.39	16.15		C7	22.45
10	14	1978-02-13 08:00	1978-02-22 21:30	1.76E+10	-2.67	-4.46	13.26	23.78	6.17E+09	0.24	3.23	18.83		M7	43.40
11	15	1978-04-08 04:00	1978-04-16 03:00	6.49E+07	-1.85	-3.48	29.86	48.62	1.23E+07	0.1	4.08	18.09		X2	3.13
12	16	1978-04-17 03:30	1978-05-05 02:30	1.14E+10	-2.37	-3.74	14.18	19.43	5.21E+09	0.33	5.69	28.06	Yes	X5	16.67
13	21	1978-09-23 11:30	1978-10-16 01:30	4.32E+09	-1.76	-3.77	13.22	26.53	1.29E+09	0.19	2.37	11.31		X1	16.71
14	24	1979-02-17 16:30	1979-02-23 08:00	1.40E+07	-1.77	-3.28	23.7	35.85	3.37E+06	0.14	4.31	18.07		X2	4.37
15	27	1979-06-06 12:30	1979-06-14 10:00	3.84E+10	-3.57	-6.83	8.02	26.15	1.24E+10	0.21	1.02	9.35		X2	21.14
16	29	1979-08-01 11:30	1979-09-01 08:00	2.30E+09	-2.36	-3.48	26.95	30.19	6.20E+08	0.17	7.8	35.85	Yes	X6	5.66
17	30	1979-09-08 12:00	1979-10-03 04:30	1.83E+08	-1.51	-3.76	19.02	42.78	3.69E+07	0.11	2.04	9.56		X2	4.40
18	31	1979-11-16 00:00	1979-11-23 12:00	9.97E+08	-2.96	-4.44	10.78	15.96	6.20E+08	0.49	5.48	32.55		M1	36.32
19	34	1980-02-05 18:30	1980-02-09 18:30	6.79E+06	-1.66	-4.19	12.81	32.42	1.85E+06	0.16	1.65	8.67		M3	32.65
20	35	1980-03-29 19:30	1980-04-08 20:00	3.01E+06	-1.59	-3.15	30.92	48.31	5.98E+05	0.1	4.58	18.33		C5	4.26
21	36	1980-07-17 15:30	1980-07-26 18:30	5.92E+09	-2.96	-6.72	7.1	26.72	1.91E+09	0.21	0.8	7.22		M3.4	25.99
22	39	1980-10-15 10:30	1980-10-24 16:30	7.76E+07	-1.89	-5.44	8.59	30.45	2.27E+07	0.18	0.91	6.71		M2.1	10.58
23	40	1980-11-09 02:00	1980-12-05 08:30	9.31E+07	-2.36	-11.29	11.38	101.68	1.96E+07	0.12	0.74	32.67		M7.2	106.87
24	41	1981-03-26 03:30	1981-04-07 20:30	1.43E+08	-2.59	-3.02	202.65	88.35	2.09E+07	0.07	83.3	345.35		M3.5	5.90
25	42	1981-04-24 04:00	1981-04-26 11:00	1.19E+08	-1.33	-3.61	13.14	30	3.43E+07	0.18	2.03	9.16	Yes	X5.9	34.01
26	43	1981-07-20 15:00	1981-07-28 07:00	3.79E+08	-2.51	-3.61	33.73	36.92	8.53E+07	0.13	8.17	38.96		M5.4	6.51
27	48	1981-10-08 03:30	1981-10-26 22:30	3.35E+09	-2.04	-3.46	31.28	44.24	6.75E+08	0.11	5.27	23.54	Yes	X3.6	4.71
28	51	1981-12-05 17:00	1981-12-14 08:00	1.80E+09	-3.18	-5.04	15.95	29.6	5.33E+08	0.19	3.28	22.39		M5.2	3.34
29	53	1982-01-29 19:00	1982-02-12 01:00	1.81E+09	-1.69	-4.3	11.26	29.41	5.14E+08	0.18	1.51	8.13		X1.1	29.49
30	54	1982-03-07 06:30	1982-03-10 08:30	4.04E+07	-2.43	-3.37	20.3	19.13	1.92E+07	0.34	12.07	54.61		X12	12.12
31	56	1982-06-03 00:00	1982-07-02 06:00	9.82E+07	-1.98	-3.65	18.16	30.19	2.80E+07	0.18	3.81	17.88		X9	33.11
32	57	1982-07-09 02:30	1982-07-27 05:00	6.21E+10	-3.23	-5.04	11.16	20.24	2.73E+10	0.32	3.37	22.43		X2.2	69.02
33	60	1982-12-25 20:00	1983-01-10 00:30	3.52E+09	-2.68	-4.71	11.77	23.9	1.23E+09	0.24	2.54	15.52		X4.1	53.49
34	61	1983-02-03 08:30	1983-02-10 04:00	1.97E+10	-3.99	-5.26	21.66	27.49	6.14E+09	0.2	6.62	46.89		X4.1	73.02
35	63	1983-06-14 18:00	1983-06-29 15:00	5.41E+06	-1.47	-3.72	27.14	61.09	9.35E+05	0.09	2.46	11.35		C2.6	5.31
36	66	1984-03-07 01:00	1984-03-23 07:00	9.56E+07	-2.43	-5.11	134.7	361.03	6.42E+06	0.02	6.57	54.9		M2	29.19
37	67	1984-04-25 09:30	1984-05-15 19:30	2.58E+09	-2.07	-4.5	23.66	57.42	1.14E+08	0.03	1.6	50.09		X13	5781.59
38	69	1985-01-22 02:30	1985-01-25 18:00	1.59E+07	-2.37	-3.98	56.09	90.79	2.23E+06	0.06	6.46	36.2		X4.7	9.39
39	71	1985-07-09 02:30	1985-07-12 13:30	7.95E+06	-1.49	-3.72	19.05	42.48	1.63E+06	0.11	2.12	9.77		M2.9	9.77
40	73	1986-02-14 10:55	1986-02-19 07:40	1.30E+08	-1.31	-3.79	9.35	23.24	4.62E+07	0.24	1.59	7.49		M6.4	14.74
41	75	1986-05-04 12:20	1986-05-05 13:15	1.04E+06	-1.23	-4.56	18.12	60.39	1.72E+05	0.08	1.16	6.86		M1.2	10.83
42	76	1987-11-07 22:45	1987-11-10 13:15	2.37E+08	-2.16	-6.33	9.56	39.93	5.37E+07	0.13	0.7	6.19		M1.2	22.20
43	77	1987-12-30 02:15	1988-01-01 02:05	4.69E+07	-2.22	-3.83	9.49	15.29	3.36E+07	0.58	5.3	26.97		C1.7	0.04
44	78	1988-01-02 23:00	1988-01-06 13:50	6.52E+08	-2.43	-5.27	17.82	50.66	1.20E+08	0.1	1.52	11.35		X1.4	0.40

Table 4. continued.

No.	No./ Start Time	End Time	C ²	γ_1	γ_2	E_0^3	E_{break}^4	C_err ²	γ_{1_err}	γ_{2_err}	$E_0_err^3$	$E_{break_err}^4$	GLE	Flare	χ^2
45	80	1988-11-08 15:45	1988-11-10 11:40	2.74E+06	-1.58	-3	31.06	44.15	5.26E+05	0.11	0.04	5.24	20.03	M3	16.81
46	83	1989-03-08 03:30	1989-03-14 19:50	1.09E+10	-2.73	-4.92	14.76	32.2	2.89E+09	0.16	0.04	2.18	13.78	X15	49.58
47	84	1989-03-23 20:15	1989-03-24 21:30	2.86E+07	-2.14	-4.69	21.4	54.58	4.87E+06	0.09	0.04	1.7	9.98	X1.5	16.92
48	85	1989-04-10 21:15	1989-04-18 01:45	1.01E+09	-1.91	-6.29	8.29	36.23	2.42E+08	0.14	0.12	0.58	4.82	X3.5	9.20
49	87	1989-05-24 05:00	1989-05-29 10:00	4.00E+07	-1.52	-7.37	6.89	40.3	1.08E+07	0.16	0.37	0.52	6.43	M5.7	74.86
50	89	1989-07-25 09:05	1989-07-26 17:45	1.50E+06	-1.17	-2.56	51.3	71.25	3.60E+05	0.11	0.02	9.25	29.34	Yes	X2.6
51	90	1989-08-12 15:45	1989-08-15 15:45	1.96E+08	-0.25	-4.52	9.64	41.11	4.12E+07	0.12	0.02	0.55	2.85	Yes	X2.6
52	91	1989-09-12 13:30	1989-09-16 01:30	6.43E+07	-1.85	-5.89	11.73	47.44	1.28E+07	0.11	0.16	0.75	6.31	M5.3	2.51
53	92	1989-09-29 11:55	1989-10-10 05:20	3.42E+08	-0.99	-2.83	24.53	44.95	6.32E+07	0.1	0.02	2.93	10.04	Yes	X9.8
54	93	1989-10-19 13:10	1989-11-09 16:50	9.14E+09	-1.35	-2.89	13.2	20.35	3.90E+09	0.3	0.02	4.26	15.74	Yes	X13
55	94	1989-11-15 07:25	1989-11-16 11:45	6.45E+06	-1.92	-3.78	328.25	608.35	3.82E+05	0.02	0.43	19.94	203.04	Yes	X3.2
56	95	1989-11-27 06:25	1989-12-05 09:05	5.86E+08	-0.3	-5.07	4.58	21.87	2.34E+08	0.28	0.02	0.46	2.76	X2.6	80.62
57	96	1990-03-19 06:30	1990-03-22 01:40	6.23E+08	-1.26	-7.1	8.23	48.12	9.05E+07	0.11	0.94	0.67	10.6	X1	231.21
58	99	1990-04-16 06:05	1990-04-23 07:15	1.89E+08	-2.26	-5.15	14.94	43.14	4.02E+07	0.12	0.15	1.45	10.31	X1.5	9.23
59	100	1990-04-28 05:30	1990-04-29 16:40	4.65E+07	-1.33	-5.38	10.63	43.04	9.74E+06	0.12	0.12	0.74	5.35	C1.2	1.04
60	102	1990-05-17 21:30	1990-05-24 19:00	1.22E+08	-1.98	-2.78	90.48	71.72	1.68E+07	0.07	0.02	18.41	66.98	Yes	X5.5
61	105	1990-07-26 04:20	1990-07-30 01:35	9.48E+08	-3.15	-3.89	55.55	41.08	2.02E+08	0.12	0.04	19.49	102.6	M2.3	31.68
62	106	1990-07-31 15:25	1990-08-06 12:05	6.18E+08	-2.01	-5.35	11.67	38.9	1.36E+08	0.13	0.1	0.96	6.69	M4.4	0.06
63	108	1991-01-27 14:45	1991-02-02 19:30	1.52E+09	-2.3	-5.81	7.29	25.61	4.80E+08	0.21	0.06	0.82	6.02	X1.3	10.45
64	109	1991-02-08 09:55	1991-02-09 17:05	2.99E+07	-1.98	-6.88	7.93	38.86	6.98E+06	0.14	0.21	0.56	5.61		42.07
65	110	1991-02-25 10:40	1991-02-27 01:55	8.08E+06	-1.53	-5.39	8.25	31.82	2.28E+06	0.18	0.12	0.85	6	X1.2	101.56
66	111	1991-03-12 18:50	1991-03-13 22:25	1.66E+06	-0.91	-5.36	8.77	39.1	3.77E+05	0.13	0.14	0.58	4.3		15.14
67	113	1991-03-23 06:40	1991-03-31 14:30	5.97E+08	-0.29	-4.29	7.58	30.29	1.72E+08	0.18	0.03	0.65	3.25	X9.4	56.71
68	114	1991-04-02 06:45	1991-04-10 01:15	1.17E+09	-2.63	-5.42	14.39	40.28	2.61E+08	0.13	0.13	1.48	10.84	M6	8.28
69	115	1991-04-22 12:00	1991-04-24 15:00	1.62E+07	-2.03	-6.58	12.33	56.08	3.84E+06	0.14	0.23	1.27	11.68		111.89
70	116	1991-05-10 15:05	1991-05-15 10:50	3.65E+08	-2.23	-3.91	32.3	54.29	5.79E+07	0.08	0.02	3.56	17.63	M8.2	24.48
71	118	1991-06-09 19:10	1991-06-15 01:30	1.73E+09	-1.97	-3.71	45.87	80.01	2.36E+08	0.06	0.02	4.07	18.95	X12	5.14
72	119	1991-06-29 21:25	1991-07-13 05:40	1.05E+10	-1.97	-5.24	7.09	23.19	3.86E+09	0.25	0.03	0.94	6.16	X1.9	59.03
73	120	1991-08-25 21:10	1991-08-30 22:30	3.70E+09	-2.76	-6.25	11.52	40.25	8.20E+08	0.13	0.13	0.94	7.94	X2.1	6.81
74	122	1991-09-30 09:40	1991-10-03 15:40	5.67E+08	-3.21	-4.44	33.13	40.94	1.19E+08	0.12	0.03	6.47	37.99	M7.3	47.14
75	124	1991-10-30 07:30	1991-10-31 20:05	7.33E+06	-1.54	-2.73	48.42	57.28	1.04E+06	0.07	0.02	7.03	24.24	X2.5	14.75
76	126	1991-12-29 05:40	1991-12-30 08:30	5.37E+07	-2.45	-5.03	5.41	13.95	4.83E+07	0.75	0.09	2.37	15.69		2.83
77	127	1992-02-06 22:45	1992-02-10 00:30	1.06E+09	-1.61	-5.43	3.46	13.23	1.04E+09	0.83	0.07	1.09	7.6	M4	0.75
78	128	1992-02-27 11:40	1992-02-28 15:05	1.22E+08	-2.85	-4.15	8.57	11.2	1.72E+08	1.29	0.06	11.42	64.54	C2.6	0.61
79	130	1992-05-09 06:15	1992-05-13 20:15	5.03E+09	-1.84	-5.15	5.98	19.81	2.31E+09	0.33	0.03	0.99	6.41	M7.4	60.54
80	131	1992-06-25 20:30	1992-07-01 23:25	4.66E+07	-0.74	-3.19	8.36	20.43	2.02E+07	0.3	0.02	1.73	6.74	Yes	X3.9
81	132	1992-08-05 20:35	1992-08-08 09:05	3.85E+07	-1.49	-10.07	5.15	44.22	1.16E+07	0.19	0.9	0.36	8.18	M4.8	97.80
82	133	1992-10-30 18:45	1992-11-01 21:20	9.78E+07	-0.32	-5	10.31	48.28	1.64E+07	0.09	0.02	0.44	2.55	Yes	X1.7
83	134	1993-03-04 13:20	1993-03-05 22:30	5.54E+06	-1.71	-3.68	22.58	44.38	1.09E+06	0.11	0.04	2.8	12.98	C8.1	41.53
84	135	1993-03-06 23:05	1993-03-09 20:10	1.64E+08	-3.06	-4.05	52.96	52.46	3.02E+07	0.1	0.18	11.98	67.66	C1.9	22.10
85	136	1993-03-12 18:50	1993-03-14 15:05	3.84E+07	-2.09	-3.28	33.13	39.39	8.12E+06	0.12	0.03	7.07	30.19	M7	8.50
86	137	1994-02-20 02:20	1994-02-22 21:20	2.14E+08	0.73	-6.7	2.55	18.95	1.04E+08	0.35	0.03	0.2	1.55	M4	30.65
87	138	1994-10-19 22:35	1994-10-21 12:05	1.51E+07	-0.18	-3.73	2.73	9.71	4.44E+07	2.9	0.03	2.84	13.59	M3.2	2.88
88	140	1997-11-06 06:00	1997-11-10 19:40	1.07E+08	-1.47	-3.04	58.41	91.92	1.30E+07	0.05	0.03	5.49	20.77	Yes	X9.4

Table 4. continued.

No.	No./ Start Time	End Time	C ²	γ_1	γ_2	E_0^3	E_{break}^4	C_err ²	γ_{1_err}	γ_{2_err}	$E_0_err^3$	$E_{break_err}^4$	GLE	Flare	χ^2
89	141 1998-04-20 12:55	1998-04-26 15:05	2.84E+07	-0.19	-5.42	12.56	65.69	4.11E+06	0.09	0.73	0.92	2.71		M1.4	43.89
90	143 1998-05-02 13:55	1998-05-04 23:05	1.33E+07	-1.47	-3.34	57.79	108.07	1.48E+06	0.05	0.03	4.23	17.44	Yes	X1.1	10.79
91	144 1998-05-06 08:25	1998-05-08 00:20	1.53E+07	-1.54	-3.15	28.04	45.04	3.00E+06	0.11	0.03	4.16	16.52	Yes	X2	6.27
92	145 1998-05-09 06:50	1998-05-11 04:10	3.42E+06	-1.38	-4.32	15.56	45.74	7.00E+05	0.11	0.16	1.41	8.59			5.57
93	146 1998-06-17 16:00	1998-06-18 23:55	1.37E+06	-1.03	-3.07	5.02	10.25	2.85E+06	2	0.06	6.42	25.88			0.19
94	147 1998-08-22 17:25	1998-08-31 20:00	2.73E+09	-2.44	-3.85	26.22	36.91	5.92E+08	0.12	0.02	4.64	23.16	Yes	X1	33.13
95	149 1998-09-30 14:25	1998-10-04 04:20	2.94E+08	-1.25	-4.24	9.77	29.22	8.62E+07	0.18	0.03	1.14	5.93		M2.8	29.84
96	152 1998-11-14 06:30	1998-11-17 15:55	1.93E+07	-1.1	-3.73	21.18	55.66	3.15E+06	0.08	0.04	1.62	7.42		C1.7	11.96
97	153 1999-01-21 00:30	1999-01-26 02:40	2.41E+08	-2.86	-4.21	34.39	46.35	4.94E+07	0.11	0.17	6.63	38.87		M5.2	18.65
98	156 1999-05-27 12:15	1999-05-28 14:40	1.31E+06	-1.42	-4.36	15.14	44.47	2.76E+05	0.12	0.16	1.41	8.7			12.42
99	157 1999-06-01 22:10	1999-06-07 15:05	1.50E+08	-1.94	-4.32	17.94	42.8	3.04E+07	0.11	0.04	1.91	10.37		M3.9	40.25
100	158 2000-02-18 08:45	2000-02-19 11:55	1.26E+06	-1.32	-5	18.42	67.72	1.29E+05	0.07	0.31	1.67	6.11		M1.3	65.29
101	161 2000-06-10 04:00	2000-06-12 21:10	3.01E+07	-2	-3.93	31.73	61.15	4.95E+06	0.08	0.05	3.39	17.01		M5.2	19.90
102	163 2000-07-13 00:30	2000-07-23 19:20	2.97E+08	-0.15	-3.63	12.05	41.98	6.15E+07	0.11	0.02	0.84	3.5	Yes	X5.7	8.90
103	164 2000-07-28 02:55	2000-07-30 09:05	7.71E+05	0.07	-10.51	4.36	46.1	2.13E+05	0.17	0.99	0.22	6.51		M1.5	88.37
104	165 2000-08-13 00:45	2000-08-15 03:30	1.05E+09	-3.09	-7.42	3.53	15.29	1.11E+09	0.91	0.83	1.27	13.94			0.00
105	166 2000-09-12 14:50	2000-09-18 01:25	1.70E+05	-2	-4.36	7.2	17.04	5.67E+08	0.28	0.08	1.45	8.13		M1	21.58
106	168 2000-10-25 15:15	2000-10-27 19:10	9.81E+07	-2.38	-5.73	12.38	41.44	2.19E+07	0.13	0.18	1.11	8.95		M2	26.81
107	170 2000-11-08 23:45	2000-11-15 17:00	6.74E+08	-0.87	-5.1	24.26	102.77	7.49E+07	0.05	0.03	0.8	4.82		M7.4	14.95
108	171 2000-11-24 07:00	2000-11-25 20:10	1.04E+08	-2.3	-3.43	41.05	46.58	1.91E+07	0.1	0.04	8.41	37.84		X2	20.94
109	176 2001-04-02 11:20	2001-04-07 08:20	1.70E+08	-1.21	-4.05	15.13	42.96	3.50E+07	0.11	0.04	1.35	6.71	Yes	X20	19.41
110	178 2001-05-07 15:00	2001-05-09 19:10	1.53E+08	-2.31	-5.45	12.14	38.1	3.36E+07	0.13	0.13	1.11	8.14			14.00
111	179 2001-05-20 08:45	2001-05-21 14:25	2.49E+05	-0.8	-2.99	22.84	49.9	2.82E+05	0.51	0.13	10.24	38.24		M6.4	15.69
112	182 2001-08-16 00:55	2001-08-26 04:40	2.69E+07	-1.13	-5.14	38.3	153.78	2.48E+06	0.04	0.04	1.26	7.95			34.27
113	183 2001-09-24 12:00	2001-10-12 03:05	2.91E+09	-1.45	-5.52	21.52	87.64	3.55E+08	0.06	0.03	0.81	5.39		X2.6	38.96
114	184 2001-10-19 04:55	2001-10-28 16:10	1.13E+08	-2.52	-3.01	148.55	73.58	1.82E+07	0.08	0.05	56.48	231.48		X1	15.29
115	185 2001-11-05 16:55	2001-11-12 20:05	8.17E+08	-0.73	-4.8	15.86	64.49	1.20E+08	0.07	0.02	0.67	3.76	Yes	X1	18.94
116	186 2001-11-17 19:55	2001-11-30 13:00	7.58E+08	-0.46	-5.08	7.77	35.84	1.81E+08	0.14	0.03	0.49	2.94		M9.9	59.82
117	188 2001-12-26 05:55	2002-01-09 07:00	1.20E+09	-2.23	-3.45	58	70.41	1.60E+08	0.06	0.02	7.64	33.95	Yes	M7.1	4.59
118	189 2002-01-10 09:55	2002-01-18 18:35	8.55E+08	-2.4	-4.96	15.84	40.58	1.77E+08	0.12	0.12	1.7	11.32		C9	2.62
119	191 2002-04-17 11:30	2002-04-28 13:35	3.81E+08	-1.14	-7.03	23.15	136.35	3.90E+07	0.04	0.05	0.61	5.34		X1.5	61.07
120	192 2002-05-22 07:50	2002-05-25 00:15	6.17E+09	-3.45	-4.55	44.37	48.82	1.14E+09	0.1	0.16	10.17	64.45		C5	0.24
121	193 2002-07-07 14:00	2002-07-09 13:55	1.67E+06	-0.83	-4.26	11.97	41	3.64E+05	0.12	0.12	0.98	5.6		M1	0.66
122	194 2002-07-16 13:20	2002-07-30 16:30	5.09E+09	-3.05	-4.46	32.46	45.49	1.02E+09	0.11	0.15	6.17	37.93		X3	1.55
123	197 2002-08-22 03:10	2002-08-27 23:10	5.75E+08	-2.22	-3.21	70.74	70.36	7.62E+07	0.06	0.02	11.44	47.89	Yes	X3.1	6.06
124	200 2002-11-09 17:10	2002-11-21 21:15	1.39E+08	-1.31	-4.81	7.65	26.73	4.25E+07	0.2	0.06	0.8	4.81		M4.6	0.46
125	205 2003-10-28 03:30	2003-10-29 16:50	9.35E+08	-0.73	-4.18	15.31	52.8	1.61E+08	0.09	0.02	0.88	4.3	Yes	X17	16.71
126	207 2003-12-02 12:50	2003-12-06 06:05	5.12E+07	-0.63	-9.87	4.41	40.73	1.33E+07	0.15	0.31	0.19	3.15		C7	59.53
127	208 2004-04-11 06:45	2004-04-12 23:05	2.70E+09	-3.51	-5	24.91	37.08	6.08E+08	0.13	0.12	4.98	33.86		C9.6	12.40
128	209 2004-07-23 15:05	2004-07-28 18:10	1.63E+09	-2.29	-5.37	11.27	34.78	4.02E+08	0.15	0.09	1.14	7.96		M1.2	0.57
129	210 2004-07-31 20:55	2004-08-02 14:45	1.27E+06	-0.33	-9.67	4.66	43.55	3.77E+05	0.18	0.76	0.28	6.17			95.19
130	211 2004-09-13 19:55	2004-09-17 18:15	4.49E+09	-2.38	-6.29	7.2	28.15	1.38E+09	0.2	0.08	0.72	5.75		M4.8	11.18
131	213 2004-11-01 06:10	2004-11-02 20:15	1.21E+06	-0.63	-3.69	14.62	44.81	2.35E+05	0.11	0.04	1.17	5.19		M1.1	22.58
132	214 2004-11-07 02:50	2004-11-09 02:45	6.63E+09	-3.09	-6.7	26.75	96.34	7.76E+08	0.06	0.13	1.42	13.72		X2	64.63

Table 4. continued.

No.	No./ Start Time	End Time	C ²	γ_1	γ_2	E_0^3	E_{break}^4	C_err ²	γ_{1_err}	γ_{2_err}	$E_0_err^3$	$E_{break_err}^4$	GLE	Flare	χ^2
133	216 2005-01-20 01:00	2005-01-21 00:00	5.07E+07	-1.01	-2.57	47.53	74.14	6.61E+06	0.06	0.02	4.75	14.88	Yes	X7.1	1.78
134	218 2005-05-13 21:00	2005-05-17 12:30	9.05E+08	-0.69	-5.78	3.65	18.53	4.69E+08	0.38	0.06	0.44	3.12		M8	15.66
135	219 2005-06-16 20:50	2005-06-18 05:55	1.78E+06	-0.83	-3.21	23.33	55.58	2.85E+05	0.08	0.04	1.92	7.49		M4	6.19
136	220 2005-07-13 18:10	2005-07-20 01:55	1.40E+08	-1.42	-4.74	11.79	39.15	3.06E+07	0.13	0.1	0.98	6.06		M5	0.53
137	221 2005-07-26 23:20	2005-08-04 21:40	7.37E+08	-2.19	-4.64	14.99	36.77	1.71E+08	0.14	0.1	1.76	10.72		M3.7	1.10
138	223 2005-09-07 23:25	2005-09-16 22:55	3.06E+10	-2.97	-5.37	155.41	371.88	2.02E+09	0.02	0.16	8.65	73.09		X17	32.98
139	224 2006-12-05 17:35	2006-12-11 08:00	3.44E+09	-2.07	-4.71	38.62	102.26	3.79E+08	0.05	0.04	2.13	12.46	Yes	X9	38.34
140	226 2010-08-18 08:50	2010-08-19 11:55	4.38E+06	-1.58	-3.63	5.88	12.06	5.04E+06	1.02	0.07	4.03	19.25			7.02
141	227 2011-03-07 23:15	2011-03-12 07:20	1.71E+08	-1.71	-5.04	10.12	33.69	4.36E+07	0.16	0.1	1.01	6.59		M3.7	3.94
142	229 2011-06-05 20:05	2011-06-12 05:30	1.85E+07	-1.41	-3.2	32.25	57.75	3.03E+06	0.08	0.04	3.59	14.36		M2.5	6.82
143	230 2011-08-04 04:35	2011-08-07 11:30	3.06E+08	-2	-3.91	17.11	32.72	7.81E+07	0.15	0.03	2.76	13.74		M9.3	26.21
144	231 2011-08-09 08:00	2011-08-10 16:20	3.04E+06	-1.37	-3.21	29.15	53.64	5.26E+05	0.09	0.04	3.28	13.14		X6.9	11.25
145	232 2011-09-06 23:45	2011-09-08 13:35	6.89E+05	-1.03	-3.74	22.54	61.15	1.11E+05	0.08	0.05	1.72	8.03		C1.4	29.00
146	236 2011-11-26 09:00	2011-11-30 00:20	6.69E+08	-1.96	-5.36	7.47	25.41	2.21E+08	0.22	0.07	0.89	6.07		C1	10.02
147	237 2012-01-26 11:25	2012-02-03 03:55	7.95E+07	-0.66	-4.1	11.91	40.98	1.60E+07	0.11	0.02	0.81	3.9		X1.52	21.52
148	239 2012-03-05 00:30	2012-03-17 02:25	4.22E+09	-1.88	-4.22	42.74	99.9	4.79E+08	0.05	0.03	2.59	13.46		X5.4	16.89
149	240 2012-05-17 02:05	2012-05-20 15:15	1.97E+08	-2.17	-2.91	110.62	81.23	2.58E+07	0.06	0.03	23	88.41	Yes	M5.7	3.99
150	241 2012-05-26 23:55	2012-05-29 04:55	1.59E+07	-0.91	-4.11	4.35	13.89	1.40E+07	0.73	0.08	1.48	7.7		C1.1	2.79
151	242 2012-06-16 09:45	2012-06-17 18:20	4.15E+08	-2.99	-4.34	9.22	12.39	4.49E+08	0.94	0.07	8.95	52.63		M1.9	2.32
152	244 2012-07-12 18:05	2012-07-13 13:00	4.63E+06	-0.04	-5.54	4.67	25.66	1.53E+06	0.22	0.07	0.34	2.33		X1.4	15.33
153	245 2012-07-17 15:50	2012-07-26 18:00	3.20E+08	-1.96	-5.24	25.24	82.86	4.06E+07	0.06	0.09	1.39	9.84		M1.8	47.88
154	247 2012-09-28 01:20	2012-10-01 03:35	9.89E+06	-1.5	-4.33	14.6	41.29	2.16E+06	0.12	0.13	1.47	8.54		C3.7	2.97
155	249 2013-03-15 19:45	2013-03-18 12:55	2.17E+08	-1.84	-9.62	5.41	42.15	6.27E+07	0.18	0.62	0.38	7.01		M1.1	89.54
156	250 2013-04-11 09:25	2013-04-14 17:00	2.84E+07	-1.35	-3.33	18	35.55	6.59E+06	0.14	0.03	2.52	10.42		M6.5	12.72
157	251 2013-05-14 07:20	2013-05-21 15:20	3.67E+08	-1.77	-5.61	8.48	32.58	9.91E+07	0.17	0.11	0.8	5.82		X1.2	13.12
158	252 2013-05-22 13:45	2013-05-25 23:35	9.07E+07	-0.02	-4.21	5.41	22.63	3.53E+07	0.26	0.03	0.59	2.95		M5	40.23
159	255 2014-02-25 10:15	2014-03-05 19:00	1.74E+08	-0.86	-3.54	5.46	14.64	1.30E+08	0.6	0.02	1.8	8.02		X4.9	20.66
160	256 2014-04-18 14:30	2014-04-21 08:55	3.34E+09	-3.11	-4.15	22.61	23.52	1.19E+09	0.24	0.03	9.2	51.28		M7.3	32.65
161	260 2015-06-18 05:05	2015-07-02 17:05	5.02E+09	-2	-6.43	6.32	27.98	1.55E+09	0.2	0.09	0.57	4.65		M2	22.17
162	261 2016-01-02 01:05	2016-01-03 12:55	2.68E+08	-3.04	-5	19.83	38.99	5.88E+07	0.13	0.15	3.04	20.84		M2.4	20.94
163	262 2017-07-14 04:50	2017-07-16 13:55	3.36E+08	-2.34	-6.52	9.54	39.84	8.13E+07	0.14	0.24	0.81	7.8		M2.4	46.82
164	263 2017-09-10 05:30	2017-09-15 12:40	4.06E+08	-1.28	-3.56	29.56	67.13	5.92E+08	0.07	0.02	2.25	9.68	Yes	X8	6.83

Notes.

- (1) Number in the SEPTEM reference event list.
(2) The normalization coefficient for Eq. 3 and its uncertainty are expressed in units of [# /cm² /sr /MeV].
(3) The parameter E_0 for Eq. 3 and its uncertainty are expressed in units of [MeV].
(4) The break-point energy for Eq. 3 and its uncertainty are expressed in units of [MeV].